

TECHNISCHE
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Data management plan (DMP)

Performance comparison AutoML vs Hill-climbing and Simmulated Annealing

PCAHSA

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1.0	2022-04-25	First version of DMP – created for start of project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published data sets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf

1. Data description

1a Lists of data sets that will be reused or produced

Reused data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	DOI and license / source	contains sensitive data
R1	Solar flares	plain text		http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/solar+flare	no
R2	Covid vaccination vs. mortality	plain text		https://www.kaggle.com/sinakaraji/covid-vaccination-vs-death/activity	no
R3	Wine quality	plain text		https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/machine-learning-databases/wine-quality/	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Data generation

All three data sets have already been existing prior the experiment. There is no information on how the data has been gathered by the original creator. There will be no newly generated data, but there are new data files from the pre-processing steps. I did not consider them as generated data, since it is the same data as from the existing data set, but in better format for the algorithms.

Data reuse

The three mentioned data sets have been reused in the form of a static download. Any changes that happened in the meantime have not been added/updated.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

There has no specific document structure been defined yet for this project.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used [at file level/at dataset level/at project level]. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data. Since most data sets come as CSV files, they are machine readable. Each attribute from the data set will be described in the README file.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

Data quality checks will be done, e.g., checks of consistency of labels, logical errors in the data, data curation or and version control during pre-processing. There are also checks for missing data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

R1 (Solar flares), R2 (Covid vaccination vs. mortality), R3 (Wine quality) will be stored in GitHub. External storage will be used because this experiment has originally been saved on GitHub and for the purpose of the course it will remain on GitHub. There is another copy of all data on a local hard drive, a home NAS and on OneDrive. Another storage location would be the original storage where we downloaded the data sets.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated. Since all used data sets are publicly available there is also no security threat when storing data on servers or locally.

Access to the data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only
R3	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service. Each data set has read and write access after downloading them.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

Ethical issues in the project have been identified and discussed with the Research Ethics Coordinator at TU Wien (<https://www.tuwien.at/en/research/rti-support/research-ethics/>). They are described in detail in separate documents. The research has not been reviewed yet by any ethics committee.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns. Further data will be made available with restrictive access. We also do not claim ownership of each data set. All sources can be found in the README on GitHub.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
R1	Open		1989-03-01	UCI Machine Learning Repository		CC BY 4.0
R2	Open		2009-10-07	Kaggle		CC ZERO 1.0
R3	Open		2021-10-11	UCI Machine Learning Repository		CC ZERO 1.0

The repository used in this project described in the following paragraph.

The UCI Machine Learning Repository is a collection of databases, domain theories, and data generators that are used by the machine learning community for the empirical analysis of machine learning algorithms. It is used by students, educators, and researchers all over the world as a primary source of machine learning data sets. As an indication of the impact of the archive, it has been cited over 1000 times. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/index.php>

No specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data

Description of protocol to access restricted data:

5b Long-term preservation and reusability

dataset ID	location for long-term storage (min. 10 years)	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
R1	UCI Machine Learning Repository		Students and general public
R2	Kaggle		Students and general public
R3	UCI Machine Learning Repository		Students and general public

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Since I am the only one of the original project working on this DMP, I will direct the data management process, revision and publication of this DMP.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR. Furthermore, no costs dedicated to replicate the experiment.